

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE STORAGE OF GRAIN MASS

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Abstract

In the practice of grain storage, 4 types of grain warehouses are mainly used: reinforced concrete elevators (monolithic or assembled), metal silos, warehouses and polyethylene sleeves. One of the options for temporary storage of grain is the use of sealed plastic sleeves. This article describes the innovations being made in the field of grain mass storage.

Keywords. Grain, grain mass, storage of grain mass, innovative technologies, food technology.

Аннотация

В практике хранения зерна в основном применяют 4 вида зерноскладов: железобетонные элеваторы (монолитные или сборные), металлические силосы, склады и полиэтиленовые рукава. Одним из вариантов временного хранения зерна является использование герметичных пластиковых рукавов. В данной статье описаны нововведения, которые осуществляются в области хранения зерновой массы.

Ключевые слова. Зерно, зерновая масса, хранение зерновой массы, инновационные технологии, пищевая технология.

INTRODUCTION

High-quality and technologically correct storage of grain can ensure its safety for more than one season. The safety of planting materials and the obtained harvest is important not only for a certain agricultural enterprise, but also the basis of the country's food security. There are different ways to store grain, but they all have one goal: to store it for its intended use at any time. This article discusses in detail all current methods of grain storage and the main technological regulations of this process.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Plastic sealed containers are mainly used in the following cases:

- in conservation of agricultural raw materials, raw materials and waste;
- during temporary storage of grain, dry and medium-dry seeds.

In polymer bags, commodity and fodder grains are stored, as well as fodder, hay, corn silage, beet pulp and high-moisture grain.

Grain temperature during storage in polyethylene bags is affected by: initial grain temperature, sunlight, heat from respiration processes, and heat exchange with air and soil. The temperature depends on the location of the grain in the casing, which leads to different temperature conditions in the layers. Over time, the temperature difference decreases.

RESULTS

The moisture content of grain stored in polyethylene bags depends on the initial moisture content of the grain, respiration processes in the grain mass, and moisture penetration from the outside. Due to the difference in temperature between day and night, moisture can move easily. This creates localized wet zones, which increases the risk of grain damage at individual points of the grain mass. The top layer is the wettest layer.

When stored in polyethylene sleeves, moisture has a dual role. On the one hand, high humidity accelerates the biological processes of grain deterioration and shortens its safe storage period. On the other hand, with an increase in humidity (due to the high intensity of respiration of all components of the grain mass), the rapid consumption of oxygen and the accumulation of carbon dioxide in the intergranular space, that is, conditions approaching the anaerobic state (oxygen-free) are created. Thus, the process of self-preservation of grain is accelerated. The balance of these two opposing processes determines the effectiveness of grain storage technology in each specific case.

CONCLUSION

From the above, we can conclude that hermetic storage of grain in plastic sleeves is an economical and environmentally friendly (so-called "green") storage method. It successfully solves a number of production, environmental and social problems (development of small and medium-sized farms). Thus, the introduction of this technology will help ensure the country's food security.

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